

THEORETICAL BASIS FOR IMPROVING THE SELF-DEVELOPMENT COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

Kaitarova N.K.

Basic doctoral student of TSPU named after Nizamy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14024485>

Abstract. *The given article emphasizes the importance of studying the theoretical foundations of improving the competencies of self-development of future primary school teachers in accordance with the requirements for teachers in the modern educational environment of the era of globalization, which can be achieved with the certain results.*

Keywords: *future primary school teacher, competence, self-development competence, modern teacher, professional competence, pedagogical competence.*

It is important to suggest that in the modern time of an increasingly globalized era, the need for specialists with comprehensive qualifications for the education system is growing every day. Because the presence of various competencies in the teaching staff for teaching a child in an era when innovative technologies are also rapidly developing serves to prevent any inconveniences. In particular, when paying attention to this issue, high level of self-development competence of future primary school teachers will greatly help in achieving the necessary goal in working with students of any knowledge and character. At the same time, for this reason, various studies are being conducted to improve the methodology of self-development competence of future primary school teachers, and this problem is being studied in depth for the modern era of education, enriched with innovative technologies and proves its relevance for educational activities.

It is worth mentioning that in order to demonstrate the necessary aspects of improving the self-development competencies of future primary school teachers, it is important first of all to pay attention to the theoretical foundations of this problem. After all, as a result of scientific research and various sources, literary studies conducted in connection with this problem, self-development competencies of future primary school teachers can be developed, typical for today's educational period of developing a methodology for improving projects. The changes occurring in the social and economic spheres of modern society have created new requirements for a professional teacher.

This should be a modern person with a wide range of professional and pedagogical competencies, able to adequately respond to new professional requirements and working conditions. Such a specialist can perform his or her functional responsibilities at a high-quality level, which is characterized by high social and professional mobility. Training a professional primary school teacher, ready to live and work in a rapidly changing society, is a strategic task facing the system of pedagogical education. That is why today the process of transition from education based on formal knowledge to an education paradigm based on competence is being resumed. With a competency-based approach, the main goal of education is not learning as such, but the ability of a specialist to implement it in a specific practical situation.

It is not a secret to anyone that in modern education, improving the self-development competencies of future primary school teachers is not enough for ensuring the acquisition of all the skills necessary for teaching and responding to their personal needs, which are important. Of

great importance is paying close attention to the theoretical foundations of improving the self-development competencies of future primary school teachers. A modern teacher must work in the context of modernization of education, which involves the introduction of new educational technologies, the use of changing curricula, and a qualitative update of the system of relations that develops between all participants in the educational process. In such conditions, improving the self-development competencies of future primary school teachers, solving the problem of forming a certain system of not only personal qualities and professional competencies of future primary school teachers, but also their self-development play a crucial role.

All of the above points are related to the relevance of the problem of improving the methodology for improving the competencies of self-development of students - future primary school teachers. In order for the solution to this problem to become a real priority of pedagogical science and practice, it is advisable to analyze the theoretical foundations for improving the competencies of self-development of future primary school teachers studying both at the domestic and international levels. It has been established that the method of developing the competencies of self-development of future primary school teachers has been studied by scientists from many countries in the form of data collection gained on the problem. It is the fact that scientific research on the concepts of "competence" and competence-based approach in education has been carried out repeatedly that shows the importance of the problem for education. The scientific research of world scientists I.A. Zimnyaya, D.A. Ivanov, L.F. Ivanova, V.A. Kalney, K.G. Mitrofanov, Yu. Reyven, G.K. Selevko, I.D. Frumin, B.I. Hasan, A.V. Khutorskoy and others, deeply reflecting the concepts of competence can be cited as an example. In addition, N.V. Kuzmina, A.K. Markova, L.M. Mitina defined the concept of "professional and pedagogical competence", and G.V. Matushevskaya, N.A. Bityutskikh, I.E. Malysheva defined the concept of "pedagogical competence" in their scientific research. Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical research by N. Kuzmina, V. Krichevsky and V. Rozumovich, it can be said that the most successful personal development of a teacher occurs only if a number of conditions are met. Examples of these include:

- the presence the same material and technical support, good social and living conditions, opportunities to implement the ideas of teachers;
- the presence of career growth prospects;
- organization of the educational process in such a way that the results of the primary school teacher's work depend, first of all, on the teacher himself, his abilities and characteristics;
- absence of contradictions between incentives and conditions for their implementation;
- material and social aspects correspond to the quantity and quality of energy and time spent by teachers.

Additionally, Yu. N. Kulyutkina emphasizes that for the successful development of a person's creative potential, some important features are necessary. These are:

- creative activity;
- originality;
- ability and desire for innovation;
- unification of ideas;
- mobilization of forces and restoration of past experience;
- the presence of developed imagination and emotional sensitivity.

Since professional self-improvement of the future teacher is relevant today as a special type of pedagogical activity, it is equally important to deepen the theoretical study on the issue of improving his self-improvement competencies. At the same time, the conditions and patterns of achieving the heights of professional mastery of the activity of the teacher are studied. Self-improvement of a teacher at a professional level is a conscious, purposeful process of increasing professional abilities and developing professionally important qualities in accordance with external social requirements, conditions of pedagogical activity and the personal development program. Therefore, based on the above, the ideas put forward by N. Kuzmina, V. Krichevsky and V. Rozumovich and Yu. N. Kulyutkina are of great importance in improving the self-development competencies of future primary school teachers. To fully understand this, it will be interesting to study in detail the research of scientists which also serves as a basis for creating various methods or projects in the most important practical part of the processes of improving the self-development competencies of future primary school teachers.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshoda Jalilova Uralovna. The importance of the issue of developing information competence in future primary school teachers. psychological and pedagogical aspects of intensive language teaching in the age of digital technologies scientific and practical conference of the republic. June 2, 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993607>)
2. Ivanov D.A., Mitrofanov K.G., Sokolova O.V. Competence-based approach in education. Problems, concepts, tools. Study guide. M: APK PRO, 2003. P. 101.
3. Kulyutkin Yu.N. The changing world and the problem of developing the creative potential of the individual. Value-semantic analysis. - St. Petersburg: 2013. P. 84.
4. On the development of self-development competence in elementary grades. Study of scientific research, innovative, theoretical and practical strategies. 1st Republican multidisciplinary scientific conference. September 24, 2022. P.100.
5. Kaitarova N.K. Self-development competence of primary school students and the role of primary school teachers in it. / Collection of the Republican scientific and practical conference on the topic "Reforms in the education system: through the eyes of scientists and youth" // Tashkent, 2022 September 29. P. 203

Recommended Internet Resources :

1. https://t.me/jalilova_dilshoda_2292
2. https://t.me/ilmiy_yordam_beraman
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru>
4. <https://kpfu.ru>
5. <https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/article/view/4012/4050>